
Research Article

A new combination in nothogenus × *Dryostichum* (Dryopteridaceae)

Rajeev Kumar Singh¹, Vineet Kumar Rawat^{1*} and Sanjeet Kumar²

¹Botanical Survey of India, Arid Zone Regional Centre, AIIMS Road, Jodhpur, Rajasthan, India

²Biodiversity and Conservation Laboratory, Ambika Prasad Research Foundation, Bhubaneswar, Odisha, India

*E-mail: rawat_vk2107@rediffmail.com; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6828-5108>

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Abstract: The nothogenus × *Polysticalpe* Fraser-Jenk. is treated as a synonym of × *Dryostichum* W.H.Wagner and a new combination × *D. mirabile* (Fraser-Jenk.) R.Kr.Singh, V.K.Rawat & Sanjeet Kumar is proposed for × *Polysticalpe mirabilis* Fraser-Jenk.

Keywords: Canada, *Dryostichum singulare*, Nepal, *Polysticalpe mirabilis*, Synonym

Introduction

× *Dryostichum* and × *Dryostichum singulare* was described by Wagner (1992) from Canada. The nothogenus × *Dryostichum* is a natural hybrid of *Dryopteris* Adans. × *Polystichum* Roth and hybrid species × *Dryostichum singulare* is a natural hybrid of *Dryopteris goldieana* (Hook. ex Goldie) A.Gray × *Polystichum lonchitis* (L.) Roth. Fraser-Jenkins (1997) described × *Polysticalpe* and × *Polysticalpe mirabilis* from Nepal. The nothogenus × *Polysticalpe* is a natural hybrid of *Diacalpe* Blume [now synonym of *Dryopteris* Adans.] × *Polystichum* Roth and hybrid species × *Polysticalpe mirabilis* is a natural hybrid of *Diacalpe aspidioides* Blume [now *Dryopteris pseudocaenopteris* (Kunze) Li Bing Zhang] × *Polystichum squarrosus* (D.Don) Fée. It is clear that the hybrid parents for both the nothogenus × *Dryostichum* W.H.Wagner and × *Polysticalpe* Fraser-Jenk. are the same *Dryopteris* Adans. × *Polystichum* Roth. Therefore, the later published nothogenus × *Polysticalpe* is synonymized under × *Dryostichum* and a new combination is made here for × *Polysticalpe mirabilis* Fraser-Jenk. under × *Dryostichum* as × *D. mirabile* (Fraser-Jenk.) R.Kr.Singh, V.K.Rawat & Sanjeet Kumar.

Nomenclature

× *Dryostichum* W.H.Wagner, *Canad. J. Bot.* 70(2): 247. 1992.

Type: × *Dryostichum singulare* W.H.Wagner

Hybrid Parentage: *Dryopteris* Adans. × *Polystichum* Roth

= × *Polysticalpe* Fraser-Jenk., *New Sp. Syndr. Indian Pteridol.* 300. 1997, *syn. nov.*

Type: × *Polysticalpe mirabilis* Fraser-Jenk.

Hybrid Parentage: *Dryopteris* Adans. (= *Diacalpe* Blume) × *Polystichum* Roth

Distribution: Canada and Nepal.

× *Dryostichum mirabile* (Fraser-Jenk.) R.Kr.Singh, V.K.Rawat & Sanjeet Kumar, *comb. nov.*

≡ × *Polysticalpe mirabilis* Fraser-Jenk., *New Species Syndr. Indian Pteridol.* 300. 1997.

Holotype: Nepal, C. Nepal, Bagmati zone, forest where road climbs up in zig-zags from 1–2 km inside the south-eastern gate no. 1 into Nagarjun Forest towards Jamachok, Southeast slope of Jamachok mountain, West of Balaju, Northwest side of Kathmandu. Kathmandu District, c 1650 m, 17 November 1989, C.R. Fraser-Jenkins 15834 (BM).

Hybrid Parentage: *Diacalpe aspidioides* Blume [= *Dryopteris pseudocaenopteris* (Kunze) Li Bing Zhang] × *Polystichum squarrosus* (D.Don) Fée

Distribution: Nepal.

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